

Synthesis, characterization, luminescence and DNA binding properties of Ln^{III} complexes with a pentadentate Schiff base ligand

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Abstract : Schiff base ligand (*N,N*-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene) 1,3-diiminopropane-2-ol) (H₃L) and its lanthanide complexes [LnL(H₂O)₂] [Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm] are synthesized and characterized based on elemental analyses, molar conductance, IR, UV-Visible, cyclic voltammetry, TGA, X-ray powder diffraction and mass spectral studies. The conductivity data show a 1 : 1 electrolyte nature with a general formula [LnL(H₂O)₂]. The IR spectra reveal coordination of the ligand through two azomethine nitrogen, two phenolic and one propanol hydroxyl of the ligand to the lanthanide ion. The complexes shows stable quasi-reversible cyclic voltammetry response in the potential range +0.68 to -1.4 V ($\Delta E_p = 0.240$ mV) at 100 mV s⁻¹ in DMF for the Pr^{III/IV} and Sm^{III/IV} redox couples in solution. The thermal decomposition studies indicate the presence of two water molecules in the inner coordination sphere. Praseodymium and samarium complexes exhibit the characteristic luminescence emission of the central metal ions attributed to efficient energy transfer from the ligand to the metal center. Further, the binding properties of these complexes with calf-thymus DNA have been investigated using absorption spectrophotometry.

Keywords : Rare earths complexes, X-ray diffraction, fluorescence, CT-DNA.

Introduction

There has been considerable interest on lanthanide complexes because of their potential applications, such as fluorescent labeling reagents, imaging agents, planar waveguide amplifiers^{1,2}, light-emitting diodes (LEDs)³ and bio-inspired luminescence probes⁴⁻⁶. Generally, Ln^{III} complexes are considered to have the brightest emission, but the luminescence efficiency of these complexes largely depends on the choice of organic ligands^{7,8}. Since the forbidden f-f transitions make direct photo excitation of lanthanide ions unfavored, the organic ligands function like an antenna by absorbing light and transferring this energy to the excited states of the central lanthanide ion. The excited lanthanide ion then undergoes radiative transitions to lower energy states resulting in characteristic multiple narrow-width emission bands and hypersensitivity to coordination environment. Schiff base metal complexes have played a key role in the development of coordination chemistry⁹. Schiff base ligands are considered as a very important class of organic compounds because of their ability to form stable complexes with many different

transition metal and lanthanide ions in various oxidation states¹⁰⁻¹⁶.

The increasing interest in the coordination chemistry of lanthanides has been focused on potential applications in catalysis^{17,18}, advanced optics¹⁹⁻²³, chemotherapy²⁴ and diagnostic medicine^{25,26}. One of the major applications of lanthanide complexes in medicine is their use as water proton relaxation agents for NMR imaging. This work focuses on the use of a Schiff base ligand (H₃L) which have selective ability to coordinate to lanthanide ions thus protect them from deactivation caused by interaction with solvent molecules and enhance their luminescence by providing proper conjugate absorption groups suitable for energy transfer and high thermodynamic stability.

In the light of the above and in continuation of our ongoing research work²⁷⁻³¹ on metal complexes of Schiff base ligands, we have investigated La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes with (*N,N*-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene) 1,3-diiminopropane-2-ol) (H₃L) ligand. In addition, the binding properties of these complexes with CT-DNA have been investigated using absorption spectrophotometry.

Experimental

Materials and methods : Lanthanide salts, $\{[\text{Ln}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]; \text{Ln} = \text{La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm}\}$ and 1,3-diaminepropan-2-ol were purchased from Sigma Aldrich chemical company. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All other solvents and reagents were of analytical grade. The metal content of the complexes was determined by titration with EDTA³² using xylenol oranges as an indicator. Elemental analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer. Molar conductivities were measured in dimethylformamide (DMF) solution, concentration of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, at 25 °C using ELICO conductivity meter equipped with CM162 conductivity cell. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model 100 spectrophotometer in the region of 4000–400 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets. The spectra were recorded at room temperature with 2 cm^{-1} resolution. UV-Visible spectra were recorded in DMF solution, concentration of $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, at 25 °C using a UV Lambda 50 Perkin-Elmer UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The cyclic voltammetric measurements were taken on a BAS CV-27 assemble in conjunction with an X-Y recorder. Measurements were made on the degassed (N_2 bubbling for 5 min) solutions in ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) containing 0.1 M tetra butyl ammonium hexafluorophosphate as the supporting electrolyte. The three-electrode system consists of glassy carbon (working) platinum wire (auxiliary) and Ag/AgCl (reference) electrode. Fluorescence spectra (scanned from 200 to 900 nm, with a spectral resolution of 0.2 nm, slit widths $\sim 2.5 \text{ nm}$) were recorded instrument model Perkin-Elmer precisely LS-55 fluorescence spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell at room temperature. The light source and detectors were 450 W xenon lamp and R955 photomultiplier tube, respectively. The thermal analysis were performed on a Perkin-Elmer Pyris STA 6000 thermo balance analyzer operating at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in the range of ambient temperature up to 900 °C under N_2 . X-Ray diffractometer (XRD) Philips : PW1830. Electron ionization-mass spectrometer, Model : AUTOSPEC-M, Micromass, UK.

DNA binding experiments : A solution of CT-DNA in 0.5 mM NaCl/5 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.0) gave a ratio of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm (A_{260}/A_{280}) of 1.8–1.9, indicating that the DNA was sufficiently free of proteins³³. A concentrated stock solution of DNA was pre-

pared in 5 mM Tris-HCl/50 mM NaCl in water at pH 7.0 and the concentration of CT-DNA was determined per nucleotide by taking the absorption coefficient ($6600 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 260 nm³⁴. Stock solutions were stored at 4 °C and were used after no more than 4 days. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare buffer solutions. Solutions were prepared by mixing the complex and CT-DNA in DMF medium. After equilibrium was reached (*ca.* 5 min) the spectra were recorded against an analogous blank solution containing the same concentration of DNA. The data were then fitted into eq. (1) to obtain the intrinsic binding constant (K_b)³⁵.

$$\frac{[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_B)}{[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_B - \epsilon_F) + 1/K(\epsilon_B - \epsilon_F)} = \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_A , ϵ_B and ϵ_F correspond to the apparent, bound and free metal complex extinction coefficients, respectively. A plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_F)$ versus $[\text{DNA}]$ gave a slope of $1/(\epsilon_B - \epsilon_F)$ and a Y-intercept equal to $1/K_b(\epsilon_B - \epsilon_F)$; K_b is the ratio to the Y-intercept.

Synthesis of Schiff base ligand : The Schiff base ligand H_3L was prepared³⁶ by mixing 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g; 10 mmol) in 20 ml of hot methanol with 1,3-diaminepropan-2-ol (0.45 g; 5 mmol) in 10 ml of methanol. The resulting reaction mixture was taken in a 100 ml round bottom flask and heated under reflux on water bath for 1 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, a crude yellow product was obtained. Then, the product was collected by filtration, washed with cold ethanol and dried. Finally, the product was recrystallized from hot ethanol. Yield : 65%; m.p. 235 °C.

Synthesis of Ln^{III} complexes : A 0.350 mmol (0.138 g) of H_3L was dissolved in 20 ml of chloroform. To this solution, a solution of $\text{Ln}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{Ln} = \text{La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm}$] (0.350 mmol) in 10 ml methanol was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h, and the yellow precipitate formed was filtered, washed with CCl_4 and dried *in vacuo*. The complex was recrystallized by slow diffusion of diethyl ether into a methanol solution of the complex. Yield : 70%.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of formulation : In the present investigations, Ln^{III} complexes of Schiff base ligand (H_3L) were synthesized and characterized based on physico-chemical and spectral techniques. The multi-step procedure leading to

the synthesis of target complexes. The ligand (H_3L) was synthesized by a conventional one-step condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 1,3-diaminepropan-2-ol. All the complexes were synthesized by reacting stoichiometric ratio 1 : 1 $[Ln(NO_3)_3 \cdot xH_2O]$ (where Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm) with the ligand H_3L yielded a series of complexes correspond to the formula of $[LnL(H_2O)_2]$ may be depicted by eq. (2).

All complexes are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, insoluble in water and diethyl ether, but slightly soluble in methanol, ethanol, ethyl acetate, chloroform, benzene and readily soluble in dimethylformamide and DMSO. The elemental analysis, compound formula, weight, yield%, and molar conductivity data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductance : Molar conductivity values for all complexes in $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ DMF solution at 25 °C, tabulated in Table 1, are in the range of 5.2–7.1 S $cm^2 mol^{-1}$ as reported for 1 : 1 electrolytes³⁷. The values suggest that the no ionic nature of the complexes.

Infrared spectroscopy : The IR band assignments are

given in Table 2. The comparison of the IR spectra of the free ligand and $[LnL(H_2O)_2]$ complexes. The bands near 1600 cm^{-1} and 1260 cm^{-1} are associated with the $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(C-O)$, respectively. The stretching frequencies change in profile in the complexes as compared to those observed for the isolated ligand. All of the complexes showed very similar infrared spectra above 400 cm^{-1} and, therefore, far-infrared spectra were recorded (400 cm^{-1}) in an attempt to assign $\nu(Ln-O)$ and $\nu(Ln-N)$ vibrational modes. There is a paucity of such assignments in the literature³⁸, though it appears that $\nu(Ln-O)$ and $\nu(Ln-N)$ might be expected in the 400–600 cm^{-1} region. In the H_3L ligand, the phenolic and propanolic $\nu(O-H)$ vibration band appeared at 3249 cm^{-1} while the coordinated vibration mode are shifted towards higher frequency region 3370–3399 cm^{-1} that was due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded in the free ligand. The staying of $\nu(O-H)$ in the complexes indicates that the phenolic and propanolic $\nu(O-H)$ oxygen is coordinated to the deprotonation of lanthanide ions. The band at 1633 cm^{-1} for the free ligand is assigned to the $\nu(C=N)$ stretch, which shifts to 1628 cm^{-1} upon coordination. This shift and the appearance of the band at 411 cm^{-1} which assigned to $\nu(Ln-N)$ confirm that the nitrogen of the azomethine group is coordinated to the lanthanide ions^{39–41}.

Table 1. Analytical data and molar conductance values for the Schiff base

Compd.	F. wt.	Found (Calcd.) (%)			Yield (%)	Λ_m (S $cm^2 mol^{-1}$)
		C	H	N		
H_3L	399.0	75.18 (75.19)	5.26 (5.28)	7.08 (7.09)	65	–
$[LaL(H_2O)_2]$	568.9	52.73 (52.72)	3.86 (3.87)	4.92 (4.93)	70	5.24
$[CeL(H_2O)_2]$	570.1	52.62 (52.65)	3.85 (3.84)	4.91 (4.81)	65	6.16
$[PrL(H_2O)_2]$	571.0	52.54 (52.55)	3.85 (3.86)	4.90 (4.92)	82	5.81
$[NdL(H_2O)_2]$	574.0	52.26 (52.32)	3.83 (3.84)	4.87 (4.86)	75	7.16
$[SmL(H_2O)_2]$	580.3	51.69 (51.72)	3.79 (3.80)	4.82 (4.78)	80	7.12

Table 2. Major infrared spectral data for the Schiff base ligand H_3L and its Ln^{III} complexes (cm^{-1}) and UV-Visible absorption bands (λ_{max}) and band assignments

Complex	$\nu(O-H)$	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu(Ar-O)$	$\nu(Ln-O)$	$\nu(Ln-N)$	λ_{max} (nm)
H_3L	3249	1633	1252	–	–	310 ^a , 403 ^b
$[LaL(H_2O)_2]$	3376	1638	1266	587	419	310 ^a , 404 ^b , 382 ^c
$[CeL(H_2O)_2]$	3394	1638	1267	587	411	310 ^a , 400 ^b , 382 ^c
$[PrL(H_2O)_2]$	3399	1638	1273	587	414	310 ^a , 402 ^b , 380 ^c
$[NdL(H_2O)_2]$	3384	1636	1268	587	412	310 ^a , 402 ^b , 382 ^c
$[SmL(H_2O)_2]$	3370	1634	1268	587	413	310 ^a , 402 ^b , 375 ^c

$a = \pi \rightarrow \pi^*$; $b = n \rightarrow \pi^*$; $c = LMCT$.

The bands at 3200–3400 cm^{-1} are affected by metal coordination. The interpretation of these bands due to the $\nu(\text{OH})$ of the phenolic groups or H_2O . The broad band of medium intensity occurring in the region is due to the symmetric and the antisymmetric $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ stretching vibrations of inner-sphere molecules which was further supported by the appearance of a new band at 1615 cm^{-1} due to the vibration mode of $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ ⁴².

UV-Visible spectroscopy : The UV-Visible absorption spectral data of the maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) and the corresponding band assignment for the ligand and its Ln^{III} complexes ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ in DMF) are listed in Table 2. The electronic spectra of ligand and its lanthanide complexes are shown in Fig. 1. The ligand (H_3L) shows three absorption bands with maxima at 310, 403 and 424 nm. The bands at 403 and 424 nm, are assigned to $n-\pi^*$ transitions of conjugation between the lone pair of electrons of (C=N) group a conjugated π bond of the aromatic ring^{43–47}. The third band at 310 arises from $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the aromatic ring. The new absorbance band observed at 382 nm complexes was attributed to the electron transfer from lanthanide metal ion and the coordinated ligand i.e. $\text{M} \rightarrow \text{L}$ charge transfer band⁴⁴. This change is essentially variant for each of the lanthanide complexes (La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}) and is attributed to metal coordination by the ligand. The higher energy band in the free ligand is observed as a single band upon complexation without much shift in frequency. Based

Fig. 1. UV-Visible absorption spectra of (a) Schiff base ligand H_3L , (b) $[\text{SmL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, (c) $[\text{PrL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, (d) $[\text{NdL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ in DMF solution at the room temperature.

Fig. 2. Tentative structure of Ln^{III} complex (where $\text{Ln} = \text{La}$, Ce , Pr , Nd and Sm).

on analytical and spectral data a general structure (Fig. 2) is tentatively assigned to the lanthanide complexes.

Cyclic voltammetric studies : The electro-chemical redox properties of the metal complexes $[\text{LnL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ [$\text{Ln} = \text{Pr}$ and Sm] have been studied employing cyclic voltammetry in the potential range +0.6 to -1.4 V recorded at 0.05, 0.075, 0.1, 0.125 and 0.150 V s^{-1} scan rate with reference to Ag/AgCl electrode at room temperature in presence of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate as a supporting electrolyte. The observed electrochemical data i.e. magnitudes of the reduction potentials (E_{pc}), oxidation potentials (E_{pa}) and half wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) along with the representative typical cyclic voltammograms are shown in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b. The cyclic voltammogram for the complex $[\text{PrL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ recorded at 0.05 V s^{-1} scan rate exhibited a weak intensity (Fig. 3a) irreversible cathodic peak at $E_{\text{pc}} = -0.92 \text{ V}$, which shows intensity variation in cathodic peaks at different scan rates. The intensity of the cathodic peak changes on increasing the scan rates from 0.05–0.150 V s^{-1} . However, the voltammogram recorded at 0.150 V s^{-1} contained an additional weak intensity anodic peak at $E_{\text{pa}} = -0.68 \text{ V}$, which can be coupled with the cathodic peak a generate flattened quasi-reversible redox couple^{48,49} with $E_{1/2} = -0.80 \text{ V}$, peak separation $\Delta E = E_{\text{pc}} - E_{\text{pa}} = 0.240 \text{ V}$ and peak current ratio $-I_{\text{c}}/I_{\text{a}} = 1.4375$. This is consistent with the formation of an anodic redox couple $\text{Pr}^{\text{III/IV}}$ involving one e^- redox process [eq. (3)].

Cyclic voltammograms of the samarium complex show (Fig. 3b) two active responses in DMF potential range of

Fig. 3(a). Cyclic voltammetric profile of $[\text{PrL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ at varying scan rates (mV s^{-1}) [0.05, 0.075, 0.1, 0.125 and 0.150].

Fig. 3(b). Cyclic voltammetric profile of $[\text{SmL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ at varying scan rates (mV s^{-1}) [0.05, 0.075, 0.1, 0.125 and 0.150].

+0.6 to -1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl, assigned to the $\text{Sm}^{\text{III/IV}}$ couple. Comparison of the $E_{1/2}$ values of present the Sm^{III} complex reveals that the complex undergo more facile redox change, which seems to complex prove that the Pr^{III} complex with positive $E_{1/2}$ values exhibit higher active than the Sm^{III} complex.

Thermogravimetric analysis : Thermogravimetric (TG) and differential thermogravimetric (DTGA) analysis were carried out for the ligand, H_3L , and its corresponding Ln^{III} complexes within the temperature range from ambient temperature up to 900 °C under N_2 flow. The correlation between the different decomposition steps of Ln^{III} complexes with the corresponding weight losses are discussed in terms of the proposed formula of the Ln^{III} complexes.

TGA results showed that the ligand is thermally stable up to 260 °C and its decomposition starts at 270 °C and finishes at 500 °C with one decomposition step (Supplementary Fig. S1). The TGA curve of Sm^{III} complex shows (Fig. 4) that the Sm^{III} complex decomposition two major steps. Generally in TG analysis, the first stage, mass loss percentage was 47.2% is consistent with theoretical value (46.5%). The decomposition temperatures of these two

Fig. 4. TGA and DTGA curves of the $[\text{SmL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex.

Fig. S1. TGA and DTGA curves of H₃L ligand.

water molecules and one ligand molecule from around 110 to 630 °C suggests that the coordinate to two crystalline water molecules present in the Sm^{III} complex bonded in the inner coordination sphere.

The second stage of decomposition in the range 630 to 900 °C due to loss of another ligand molecule with a weight loss of 38.3% is consist with theoretical value (38.1%). The decomposition starts from around 700 °C and continues up to around 900 °C, could be attributed is obtained which indicates the formation of stable Sm₂O₃. The weight of Sm₂O₃ oxide agrees with the calculate values.

Based on these data, the complex compound are proposed general formula [LnL(H₂O)₂] to have the conformation shown in Fig. 2.

X-Ray powder diffraction studies : X-Ray diffraction studies of the powder sample were carried out as it could not be possible to grow suitable crystals for complete X-ray analysis. The observed interplanar spacing values (*d* in Å), have been measured from the diffractogram of the [NdL(H₂O)₂] complex (Supplementary Fig. S2), with respect to major peaks having relative intensity at wavelength = 1.54178 and the Millar indices, *h*, *k*, *l* have

been assigned to each *d* value and 2θ angles are reported shown given in Table 3. The system belongs to 'Orthorhombic' form. The direct unit cell dimensions determined are : *a* = 8.2641 Å, *b* = 9.1220 Å, *c* = 10.5890 Å, *V* = 798.2515 (Å)³, α = β = γ = 90°.

Based on the experimental evidences average crystal size 24 nm to 36 nm.

Mass spectral studies : In the present investigation, the EI-MS spectrum of HNDP showed the formation of a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 399 corresponding to the total molecular weight of the ligand (Supplementary Fig. S3). The complex molecular ion peak *m/z* 572 detected by mass-spectral fragmentation analysis (Supplementary Fig. S4). Also the Pr^{III} complex confirm the stoichiometry ratio of the 1 : 1 type proposed structure.

Luminescence spectroscopy of complexes : The fluorescence spectra of the ligand and its Ln^{III} complexes (1.0 × 10⁻⁵ M in DMF solution) were recorded at the room temperature. The details of the emission characteristic of the ligand and its Ln^{III} complexes are listed in Table 4. The emission spectrum (Fig. 5a) of the free ligand H₃L exhibits broad fluorescence band centered at 465 nm attributed to π-π* transitions^{44,45}. Inspection of emission

spectra ($\lambda_{exc} = 318$ nm) shown in Fig. 5b and Fig. 5c together with the data listed in Table 4, indicate that [PrL(H₂O)₂] and [SmL(H₂O)₂] complexes exhibit the characteristic emission spectra of the Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} ions re-

spectively. This indicates that the ligand H₃L is a good chelating organic chromophore and can be used to absorb and transfer energy to the Ln^{III} ions.

The room temperature emission spectra of the praseody-

Fig. S2. X-Ray powder diffraction of the [NdL(H₂O)₂] complex (original graph).

Fig. S3. Mass spectrum of ligand HNDP (H₃L).

Table 3. X-Ray diffraction data of the [NdL(H₂O)₂] complex

<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>	2θ (Exp.)	2θ (Calcd.)	2θ (Diff.)	<i>d</i> (Exp.)	<i>d</i> (Calcd.)	Intensity (Exp.)
1	0	2	20.451	20.467	-0.016	4.3394	4.3310	90.5
1	2	0	21.952	22.022	-0.070	4.0461	4.0481	56.3
1	2	1	23.758	23.762	-0.004	3.7434	3.7401	81.6
2	1	1	25.157	25.177	-0.020	3.5381	3.5222	80.4
1	2	2	28.359	28.342	0.016	3.1456	3.1014	53.3
2	1	2	29.255	29.274	-0.019	3.0508	3.0544	32.6
0	3	1	30.451	30.453	-0.002	2.9332	2.9021	48.7
2	1	3	34.652	34.640	0.012	2.5867	2.5875	64.9
1	0	3	40.952	40.941	0.011	2.2021	2.0020	69.5
3	1	3	42.951	42.974	-0.023	2.1041	2.1087	78.0
1	4	2	44.652	44.642	0.010	2.0278	2.0281	100.0
1	5	1	52.258	52.256	0.002	1.7494	1.7440	67.9
5	2	2	62.754	62.744	0.010	1.4795	1.4802	49.4

Table 4. Luminescence spectra data of the Schiff base ligand H₃L at the room temperature

Compd.	λ _{ex} (nm)	ν (cm ⁻¹)	λ _{em} (nm)	ν (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments
H ₃ L	318	31446	465 ^a	20833	π→π*
[LaL(H ₂ O) ₂]	318	31446	470 ^a	21276	π→π*
[CeL(H ₂ O) ₂]	318	31446	465 ^a	21505	π→π*
[NdL(H ₂ O) ₂]	318	31446	464 ^a	21551	π→π*
			318 ^a	31446	π→π*
[PrL(H ₂ O) ₂]	318	31446	455 ^a	21978	S ₀ →S ₁
			565	17699	³ P ₀ → ³ H ₅
			625 ^b	16000	¹ D ₂ → ³ H ₄
			648	15432	³ P ₀ → ³ F ₂
			318 ^a	31446	π→π*
[SmL(H ₂ O) ₂]	318	31446	475 ^a	20052	S ₀ →S ₁
			558	17912	⁴ G _{5/2} → ⁶ H _{3/2}
			580	17241	⁴ G _{5/2} → ⁶ H _{5/2}
			637 ^b	15698	⁴ G _{5/2} → ⁶ H _{7/2}
			658	15197	⁴ G _{5/2} → ⁶ H _{9/2}

^aBroad; ^bSharp.

Fig. 5. Excitation (dash line) and emission (straight line) spectra of (a) H₃L, (b) [PrL(H₂O)₂], (c) [SmL(H₂O)₂] in DMF at room temperature. The excitation spectrum was obtained by monitoring the 625 nm emission (¹D₂→³H₄) of Pr^{III} complex and 637 nm emission (⁴G_{5/2}→⁶H_{7/2}) of Sm^{III} complex. The emission spectrum was recorded using the 318 nm excitation (S₀→S₁).

mium compound are shown in Fig. 5b. The 625 nm emission line was monitored to obtain the excitation spectrum. Which consists of an intense ligand-centered transition band and several weak peaks corresponding to f-f transition of Pr^{III}. Three peaks are found in the emission spectrum. The spectrum was recorded using the S₀→S₁ excitation. The intense peak centered at ¹D₂→³H₄ transition,

but it is also believed to be overlapping with much a weaker peak corresponding to the ³P₀→³H₅ transition. The very weak emission peaks at 550 and 660 nm correspond to transition from the ³P₀ emissive state to ³H₅ and ³F₂ levels, respectively. Under the excitation of 318 nm, the emission spectrum (Fig. 5b) of the Pr^{III} complex displays three characteristic Pr^{III} emission peaks in the region 555–660 nm corresponding to the ³P₀→³H₅ (565 nm), ¹D₂→³H₄ (625 nm) and ³P₀→³F₂ (648 nm) respectively³⁸. The emission spectrum (Fig. 5c) of the Sm^{III} complex displays four characteristic Sm^{III} emission peaks in the region 555–670 nm corresponding to the ⁴G_{5/2}→⁶H_{3/2} (558 nm), ⁴G_{5/2}→⁶H_{5/2} (580 nm), ⁴G_{5/2}→⁶H_{7/2} (637 nm) and ⁴G_{5/2}→⁶H_{9/2} (658) respectively^{45,46}.

The weak broad emission band in the spectra of Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes is attributed to the fluorescence of the H₃L. However this band is almost invisible for the case of Sm^{III} complex. This indicate that the ligand to metal energy transfer process in the Sm^{III} complex is more efficient than that in Pr^{III} complex. This may be due to the better matches between the lowest triplet state energy level of the (T₁) of the ligand and the lowest resonance energy level of the Pr^{III} (¹D₂, 16000 cm⁻¹) ion as compared to that of Sm^{III} (⁴G_{5/2}, 15698 cm⁻¹) ions. It must be

Fig. 6. (a) Absorption spectra of complex $[LaL(H_2O)_2]$ in the presence of increasing amount of CT-DNA. Arrows shows the absorbance changes upon increasing CT-DNA concentration. $\lambda_{nm} = 398$ free; 400 bound [(1) No DNA added; (2) 0.9850×10^{-8} ; (3) 1.9603×10^{-8} ; (4) 2.9261×10^{-8} ; (5) 3.8823×10^{-8} ; (6) 4.8892×10^{-8} ; (7) 5.7669×10^{-8} ; (8) 6.6956×10^{-8} ; (9) 7.6138×10^{-8} ; (10) $8.5268 \times 10^{-8} = \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$] and (b) A plot of $[DNA]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_F)$ versus $[DNA]$ for titration of DNA with $[LaL(H_2O)_2]$ [$K_b = 9.2 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$].

here mentioned that the small energy gap could result in a back-energy transfer process from the excited resonance level of the Pr^{III} to the T_L of the ligand H_3L , therefore leading a depression in the luminescence output of the Sm^{III} and Pr^{III} ions⁴⁷⁻⁵¹.

Although different paths have been suggested for the energy transfer from T_L to the resonance state of Ln^{III} ions in lanthanide complexes. The favourite mechanism involves strong absorption of UV energy that excites the ligand to the excited singlet state (S_L), followed by an energy migration via non-radiative intersystem crossing to the T_L . The energy is then transferred intermolecularly from the T_L to a resonance state of the Ln^{III} ion, from which the luminescence in the visible region occurs. To luminescence, the T_L level must be nearly equal or lie above the resonance energy level of the Ln^{III} ions. If the energy gap between the T_L and the lowest resonance energy level of the Ln^{III} ion is low then the back transfer

from the lanthanide ion to the ligand can occur which reduces the intensity of the luminescence. Our results of the luminescence experiments were consistent with the proposed mechanism for intermolecular energy transfer⁵²⁻⁵⁴.

For the case of $[LaL(H_2O)_2]$, La^{III} has no 4f electron and no excited states below the T_L , which is much higher in energy than the S_L and T_L of the ligands. Therefore, the energy absorbed by the ligand cannot be transferred to either La^{III} ion by an intermolecular energy transfer process, however relaxes through its own lower energy levels. Therefore the emission bands observed in the emission spectra of La^{III} complex at 470 nm respectively, are due to the fluorescence of the ligand. The red shift in the fluorescence band of the ligand in Ln^{III} complexes compared with the free ligand can be attributed to coordination of Ln^{III} ions to the ligand. This results in increasing of the delocalization of electrons and reducing the energy

Fig. S4. Mass spectrum of the $[\text{PrL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex.

gaps between the molecular orbitals of the ligand^{45,55}.

Furthermore, the emission spectra of Ce^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes exhibit a single broad emission band at 465 nm and 464 nm respectively, which are attributed to π - π^* transitions of the ligand. The appearance of the strong fluorescence characteristic of the ligand H_3L and the absence of the characteristic emission bands of Ce^{III} and Nd^{III} ions is probably due to the large energy gap between the T_L of the ligand and their lowest resonance energy levels.

DNA binding studies : The interaction of lanthanide complexes with CT-DNA was investigated using absorption spectroscopy. The electronic spectra of $[\text{LaL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ in the absence and presence of CT-DNA are given in Fig. 6a. The binding plot is given in Fig. 6b.

In the presences of increasing amount of CT-DNA, the $[\text{LaL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex showed an decrease in intensity

[hypochromicity ($68.02 \pm 0.5\%$)] and bathochromic shifts [maximum (2 ± 1) nm] for their red shift absorption maxima. The value of K_b evaluated for the complex using eq. (1) is found to be $9.2 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$. On addition of CT-DNA to the Ln^{III} complexes, there is decreasing in molar absorptivity as well as a significant shift in λ_{max} . The decrease in absorption intensity and significant shift in wavelength is attributed to hypochromism and bathochromism, which suggests that the complex is bound to CT-DNA strongly. During these titrations, the change in the absorption values with increasing amount of CT-DNA was used to evaluate the intrinsic binding constants (K_b) for the complexes. The values of K_b evaluated for the complexes using eq. (1).

Conclusions

A penta-dentate Schiff base ligand H_3L and its lanthanide complexes $[\text{LnL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, (where, $\text{Ln} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}$,

Pr, Nd and Sm) were synthesized and characterized. Under UV light excitation, the Pr³⁺ and Sm³⁺ complex exhibits characteristic luminescence of trivalent metal ions, which indicates that the ligand is good organic chelator to absorb and transfer energy to metal ions. The Schiff base ligand binding the metal ion through the two azomethine nitrogen atoms, two phenolic and one propanolic hydroxyl groups. Two water molecules act as coordinate ligand. In addition, the participation of molecules in coordination led to the coordinate Ln^{III} complexes [with a coordination number of 7]. The energy gap between the lowest triplet state level of the Schiff base and lowest excited state level of Pr³⁺ and Sm³⁺ favor to the energy transfer process for Pr³⁺ and Sm³⁺. Thus, the present results demonstrated that the Schiff base complexes of lanthanide nitrate can be a candidate as a luminescent in super molecular nano devices and laser materials. In absorption spectra, the change in peak intensity is analogous to observations made for similar complexes. The XRD patterns of the neodymium(III) complex were recorded and the particle size of the metal complex was calculated. The stabilizes Pr^{III/IV} and Sm^{III/IV} complexes redox couples in the solution as evidenced from CV studies. The intrinsic DNA binding constants (K_b) of these complexes (10^5 – 10^7 M⁻¹) are quite high. Therefore, the complexes may be regarded as efficient intercalators of DNA.

Supplementary information

TGA and DTGA curves of H₃L ligand (Supplementary Fig. S1), X-ray powder diffraction of the [NdL(H₂O)₂] complex (Supplementary Fig. S2) and mass spectrum of ligand and Pr^{III} complex (Supplementary Figs. S3,4).

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